

1 **The role of transcription factor StBEL11 in carbon**
2 **allocation and tuberization in cultivated potato differs**
3 **from that known for the model Andean genotype**

4 Running title: Tuberisation and C dynamics in BEL11 RNAi cultivated
5 potato

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1 Abstract

2 StBEL11 is known as a negative regulator of tuberization in the Andean potato (*Solanum*
 3 *tuberosum* ssp. *andigena*). This study focuses on its role in the common potato ssp.
 4 *tuberosum* by analysing transgenic lines of cv. Kamýk with downregulated *StBEL11*
 5 expression. As expected, these lines showed enhanced tuber induction on nodal segments
 6 cultivated *in vitro* on high-sucrose medium. However, intact plants *ex vitro* exhibited
 7 significantly delayed tuberization and decreased yield, which surprisingly applied especially
 8 for lines with the most enhanced *in vitro* tuberization. Interestingly, reduced leaf *StBEL11*
 9 expression was accompanied by decreased leaf expression of positive tuberization regulator
 10 *StBEL5*, but not of *SP6A* tuberigen. The transgenics showed increased photosynthetic
 11 activity, which was not, however, associated with non-structural carbohydrate
 12 accumulation. Unexpectedly, *StBEL11* downregulation altered assimilate allocation in
 13 favour of roots over shoots and stolons before the tuberization onset, and in lines with the
 14 strongest phenotype, also during the early stage of tuberization, which likely explains their
 15 reduced tuber yields. The unexpected differences in tuber induction and yield between
 16 *andigena* and *tuberosum* lines with downregulated *StBEL11* indicate changes in the
 17 strength/hierarchy of individual components of the tuberization regulatory network and point
 18 to the impossibility of easy knowledge transfer from Andean to cultivated potato.

19

20 Highlights

21 RNAi-induced downregulation of BEL11, proposed negative regulator of tuberization in
 22 Andean potato, resulted in markedly different effects on tuberization, photosynthetic
 23 characteristics and biomass allocation in cultivated potato genotype.

24

25 Keywords

26 BEL1-like transcription factor, biomass allocation, carbohydrates, phloem exudates,
 27 photosynthesis, RNAi, *Solanum tuberosum* ssp. *tuberosum*, source-sink interactions,
 28 *StBEL11*, tuberization

29 Abbreviations

30 DAT days after transfer
 31 LD long day
 32 POTH1POTATO HOMEBOX 1
 33 RNAi RNA interference

- 1 SD short day
- 2 SP6A SELF-PRUNING 6A
- 3 WT wild type

4 Introduction

5 The potato (*Solanum tuberosum*) is the fourth most important crop worldwide, playing a
6 crucial role in the human diet due to its rich nutrient content. Potato tubers, the underground
7 storage organs, provide significant amounts of carbohydrates, dietary fiber, vitamins,
8 proteins and minerals (Zaheer and Akhtar, 2016). Potatoes have long been a staple food in
9 many countries, and their cultivation is expanding globally due to their adaptability to
10 different conditions and their important contribution to food security. Significant increases
11 in production have recently occurred in China, India, and various African countries (Devaux
12 *et al.*, 2020). To meet future demands, progress in potato cultivation and yields through
13 knowledge-based breeding is essential. Tuberization, tuber formation from the tip of below-
14 ground stems, stolons, is regulated by a complex interplay of genetic, metabolic, and
15 environmental factors (reviewed e.g. by Zierer *et al.*, 2021). While an environmental effect on
16 tuberization (e.g. photoperiod, temperature, nitrogen availability) has long been recognized,
17 the molecular mechanisms underlying tuber formation have only recently been explored.
18 Understanding the regulation of tuberization is essential for several reasons: breeding of
19 varieties with enhanced yield, resistance to pests and diseases, and improved adaptability
20 to changing environmental conditions, which is crucial for ensuring food security in the face
21 of climate change. Indeed, climate scenarios predict a global decline in potato yields of up
22 to 26% by 2085 (Raymundo *et al.*, 2018), and in Europe even up to 84.6 % (Gouerou *et al.*,
23 2025). To date, molecular research predominantly using the model genotype of ssp.
24 *andigena*, has provided just basic insights into key regulatory biomolecules, (proteins, RNAs,
25 and phytohormones) driving tuberization (e.g. Kondhare *et al.*, 2020). Interestingly, tuber
26 initiation shares some features with flowering onset, particularly in place of signal
27 production and its mobility (Abelenda *et al.*, 2014). Navarro *et al.* (2011) demonstrated that
28 SELF-PRUNING 6A (SP6A), a homolog of the florigen FLOWERING LOCUS T, responds to
29 environmental cues and acts as a long-distance tuberization signal. Under favourable
30 conditions, SP6A protein is produced in leaves and transported via the phloem to stolons,
31 where it interacts with FLOWERING LOCUS D-like and 14-3-3 proteins to form a tuberigen
32 activation complex; this regulates the expression of target genes (Teo *et al.*, 2017; Wang *et al.*,
33 2023). Notably, the mobile tuberigenic signal is more complex and comprises other
34 mobile signals including transcripts for the BEL1-LIKE (BEL) and KNOTTED1-like HOMEBOX
35 (KNOX) transcription factors, specifically *BEL5*, *BEL11*, and *BEL29* mRNAs from the BEL
36 family, and *POTATO HOMEBOX 1 (POTH1)* mRNA from the KNOX family (Banerjee *et al.*,

1 2006; Ghate *et al.*, 2017; Mahajan *et al.*, 2012; recently reviewed by Zounkova *et al.*, 2024).
2 While BEL5 and POTH1 were identified and characterized earlier, the functions of BEL11 and
3 BEL29 remain much less explored. In various potato genotypes, over-expression of *BEL5* as
4 well as *POTH1* positively correlates with enhanced tuber yields (Chen *et al.*, 2003; Cho *et al.*,
5 2015; Rosin *et al.*, 2003; Sharma *et al.*, 2016). Further, BEL5 and POTH1 were shown to form
6 a heterodimer that regulates the expression of target genes by binding to their promoter
7 sequence containing tandem TTGAC core motifs (Chen *et al.*, 2004; Chen *et al.*, 2003; Lin *et al.*,
8 2013; Sharma *et al.*, 2016). These target genes include, among others, *SP6A*, thus
9 amplifying the tuberigenic signal (Sharma *et al.*, 2016). Other target genes encode proteins
10 involved e.g. in metabolism regulation, phytohormone transport and signalling, cell cycle
11 control, and carbohydrate transport (Chen *et al.*, 2004; Chen *et al.*, 2003; Lin *et al.*, 2013;
12 Sharma *et al.*, 2016). In contrast, BEL11 and BEL29, were proposed to be negative regulators
13 of tuberization, counteracting the effect of BEL5. However, it has been only shown in the
14 strictly short-day (SD) tuberizing potato genotype of *ssp. andigena* (Ghate *et al.*, 2017).
15 Molecular mechanisms underlying BEL11 and BEL29 action remain unclear as the
16 knowledge so far only comes from a single study. BEL11 and BEL29 also possess putative
17 DNA-binding domains, but their ability to enter the nucleus, bind to target gene promoters,
18 and therefore function as transcriptional regulators has yet to be validated. Since all three
19 mentioned BEL proteins can interact with POTH1, BEL11 and BEL29 might negatively affect
20 BEL5 function by competing for the POTH1 interaction partner (Ghate *et al.*, 2017).

21 Considering the extreme genomic diversity of potato, shaped by both, wild hybridization as
22 well as domestication (Hardigan *et al.*, 2017), we wondered whether the negative effect of
23 BEL11 on tuberization, previously demonstrated in potato landrace of *ssp. andigena*, is
24 conserved in cultivated potato of *ssp. tuberosum*. Although the two subspecies differ in
25 several traits, including environmental adaptations (e.g., long-day (LD) tuberization in *ssp.*
26 *tuberosum*) and patterns of biomass allocation, the underlying differences in the functioning
27 of regulatory pathways remain largely unknown. To investigate this, we generated transgenic
28 lines of *ssp. tuberosum* cv. Kamýk that expressed part of the *BEL11* gene in the antisense
29 orientation to down-regulate expression of the native *BEL11* gene by RNA interference,
30 hereinafter called BEL11 RNAi lines. To thoroughly characterize these lines, we evaluated
31 tuberization under a set of cultivation regimes, quantified selected transcript levels,
32 carbohydrate production and distribution, growth characteristics and biomass allocation.
33 Interestingly, the effects of *BEL11* down-regulation differed from those described in *ssp.*
34 *andigena*, as weakening this hypothetical tuberization inhibitor did not lead to the expected
35 enhancement of tuberization but, surprisingly, resulted in significant suppression under
36 natural-like conditions. These differences were likely related to the observed positive effects

1 of *BEL11* down-regulation on photosynthetic activity and to altered biomass allocation within
2 the plant body.

3 **Methods**

4 **Preparation of potato transgenic lines**

5 To generate *BEL11* RNAi suppression lines, we employed the potato (*Solanum tuberosum*)
6 cultivar Kamýk that is a traditional, intermediate to late maturing, easy transformable
7 genotype sourced from the breeding station Sativa Keřkov, a.s., the Czech Republic. We
8 utilized a construct comprising a 401 bp fragment containing a unique region of *BEL11*
9 coding sequence (CDS), along with a small portion of the 5'UTR, both in antisense
10 orientation, under the control of the *CaMV 35S* promoter, cloned into the binary vector
11 pCB201 (Ghate *et al.*, 2017), kindly provided by Prof. D. Hannapel from Iowa State University,
12 USA. The transformation process was mediated by *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain
13 C58C1. The stably transformed plant lines were obtained through the transformation of leaf
14 explants and *de novo* regeneration, employing a modified protocol of Dietze *et al.* (1995).
15 Stable transformation of the regenerated plants was verified by PCR using transgene-specific
16 primers (Supplementary Table S1). DNA isolation was carried out using a modified rapid DNA
17 isolation protocol based on Edwards *et al.* (1991) (with an additional step of chloroform
18 purification and DNA dissolution in 100 μ l of 2mM Tris buffer, pH 8.5). The positively
19 genotyped lines were then tested for the level of *BEL11* transcript by RTqPCR (for details see
20 Transcript levels determination) and four lines with significantly decreased *BEL11* transcript
21 level selected for further experiments.

22 **Plant cultivation**

23 *In vitro*

24 Plant maintenance and multiplication under *in vitro* conditions were carried out using single
25 node cuttings taken from 4-week-old *in vitro* plants cultivated on Murashige and Skoog
26 medium (MS, Murashige and Skoog, 1962) either mixotrophically (3% sucrose; w/v) or
27 photoautotrophically (without sucrose, gas-permeable lid; for details see Sevcíková *et al.*
28 (2019), under LD photoperiod (16/8), photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) of 150 μ mol
29 $\text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and warm white fluorescent tube light, 22 \pm 2°C.

30 *Ex vitro* in hydroponics

31 For hydroponic cultivation we used a Low-density growing system (Araponics, Liège,
32 Belgium). The holders in the lid were modified to enable “underground” shoot (stolon) growth
33 of potato plants after *ex vitro* transfer. Roots and a part of the *in vitro*-arisen shoot (comprising
34 always the same number of nodes) of *in vitro* mixotrophically pre-cultivated plants were

1 placed below the lid. Per hydroponic system, 12 plants were used and cultivated in 1.5 l of
2 modified $\frac{1}{4}$ Hoagland solution (Hoagland and Arnon, 1938), PAR $120 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, white LED
3 supplemented with far red LED light, $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

4 *Ex vitro* and tuber-derived plants in soil

5 *In vitro* mixotrophically pre-cultivated plants (4 weeks) were used for *ex vitro* experiments
6 performed under LD photoperiod (16/8), PAR $310 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, combination of warm white
7 and cool white fluorescent tube light, $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (cultivation chamber) or LD-adjusted
8 photoperiod (16/8), $18 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ (greenhouse). Alternatively, post-dormant tubers of comparable
9 size (weight about 10-15 g) were planted in a greenhouse under the same conditions. Plants
10 were cultivated either in 7 l pots (greenhouse tuberization) or 1 l pots (other experiments);
11 substrate consisted of common garden substrate, compost soil, sand, perlite (6:2:1:2).

12 **Tuberization experiments**

13 *In vitro*

14 Single-node segments with removed leaf blades were excised from mixotrophically *in vitro*
15 grown plants and cultivated for 5 weeks (35 days after transfer, DAT) on tuber-inducing
16 medium (TIM: MS with 0.2 mg.l^{-1} 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP) and 8% of sucrose (w/v)); under
17 constant darkness, $22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. The number of micro-tubers was evaluated weekly (7, 14, 21, 28
18 and 35 DAT); all other parameters were determined 35 DAT.

19 *Ex vitro* in hydroponics

20 *In vitro* mixotrophically pre-cultivated (4 weeks) plants were used and cultivated under SD
21 photoperiod (8/16). The appearance and number of tubers were recorded weekly (7, 14, 21,
22 28 and 35 DAT), all other parameters at 35 DAT.

23 *Ex vitro* and tuber-derived plants grown in soil

24 For tuberization experiments, plants were cultivated in the cultivation chamber and in the
25 greenhouse. All parameters were evaluated at the end of the vegetation period (130 DAT).

26 **Growth characteristics**

27 Growth characteristics were evaluated in non-induced plants, as well as in plants with
28 initiated tuberization. Non-induced plants were cultivated either photoautotrophically *in*
29 *vitro* or *ex vitro* in hydroponics (after 3-weeks of mixotrophic pre-cultivation *in vitro*); under
30 LD photoperiod (16/8); growth characteristics were evaluated 21 DAT. Plants destined for
31 tuber induction were cultivated *ex vitro* in hydroponics (after 4 weeks of mixotrophic pre-

1 cultivation *in vitro*) under SD photoperiod (8/16); growth characteristics were evaluated 28
2 DAT (pre-tuberization stage) and 41 DAT (early tuberization stage).

3 **Photosynthetic characteristics**

4 Photosynthetic characteristics were determined 21 DAT in *ex vitro* soil-grown plants
5 cultivated in a cultivation chamber.

6 The net photosynthetic rates of intact fully developed leaves (6 cm² measured) were
7 determined gasometrically using a LI-6400 portable gas analyzer (LI-COR, Lincoln, NE, USA)
8 at 21°C, 500 μmol CO₂.mol⁻¹. Light exposure protocol consisted of a 10-min dark adaptation
9 phase and subsequent irradiations in the following sequence: 100, 300, 500, 700, 900 μmol
10 photons m⁻² s⁻¹ (5-min interval each). The measured values were collected at 1-min intervals.

11 The fast fluorescence kinetics was determined on dark-adapted intact leaves using a pocket
12 fluorometer FluorPen 2 (PSI, Photon System Instrument, CZ). The measurements were
13 repeated at 2 positions on the leaf blade. The maximum quantum yield of primary PSII
14 photochemistry was calculated as (F_m-F_o)/F_m, where F_m is the maximum value of
15 fluorescence under saturating irradiance and F_o is the initial fluorescence value.

16 Photosynthetic pigment content: cut-outs from fully developed leaves (81 mm²) were
17 plunged in 4 ml of N,N-dimethylformamide and incubated in darkness at 4°C for one week to
18 extract the photosynthetic pigments. The pigment contents (chlorophyll a and b and total
19 carotenoids) were determined spectrophotometrically (Evolution 201, programme Thermo
20 insight) by measuring absorbance at 480, 647, 664, and 750 nm; and calculated according to
21 Wellburn (1994).

22 **Carbohydrate content determination**

23 Tissue carbohydrate contents were determined in soil-grown *ex vitro* plants (cultivation
24 chamber, LD photoperiod, 16/8) and in hydroponically cultivated plants under both, LD
25 (16/8) and SD (8/16) photoperiod.

26 Samples (50–150 mg FW) of the leaves, stolons/tubers and roots collected 21 DAT (LD), 28
27 and 41 DAT (SD) were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen, then freeze-dried and boiled in
28 80% methanol (v/v) at 75°C for 15 min. The solvent was then vacuum-evaporated and the
29 residue resuspended in Milli-Q ultrapure water (Millipore, Bedford, MA) before being purified
30 by centrifugation and filtration. The content of non-structural soluble carbohydrates was
31 determined using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) as described in
32 Kofronová *et al.* (2020). The starch in the pellets after the soluble carbohydrates extraction
33 was hydrolyzed in 0.5 ml of 0.1M Na-acetate buffer (pH 4.5) by autoclaving and then
34 enzymatically cleaved with α-amylase (Fluka, 30U/sample) and amyloglucosidase (Sigma,

1 60U/sample) at 40°C overnight, the solvent was then vacuum-evaporated and the pellets
2 processed similarly to soluble saccharide samples and measured by HPLC (Kofronová *et al.*,
3 2020). Starch content was expressed as the amount of glucose per dry weight unit. The data
4 were evaluated using Clarity 7.2 software (DataApex).

5 **Transcript levels determination**

6 To evaluate the extent of RNA interference, the levels of *BEL11* mRNA (target gene) were
7 determined in leaves of 4-week-old *in vitro* plants. Subsequently, more detailed
8 quantification of *BEL11* mRNA and other selected transcripts (*BEL5*, *BEL29*, *POTH1* and
9 *SP6A*) was performed in the source and sink organs (leaves, stolons and roots) of *ex vitro* soil
10 cultivated plants, grown in the cultivation chamber. Moreover, *BEL11* transcript levels were
11 also examined in phloem exudates (see Phloem exudation). To compare with later
12 developmental stage, transcript analysis was also performed in leaves and young tubers of
13 SD-induced plants grown in hydroponics. Total RNA was isolated from plant material (except
14 tubers) using the TRI reagent isolation protocol (Sigma Aldrich). For tuber samples (rich in
15 starch), we employed the RNeasy PowerPlant Kit (QIAGEN). The root samples were further
16 purified using RNA Clean and Concentrator kit (Zymo Reserach, USA) according to the
17 instructions of the manufacturer. RNA integrity was checked by RNA denaturing agarose gel
18 electrophoresis (Masek *et al.*, 2005). 8 µg of total RNA from each sample were reverse-
19 transcribed using 200 U of RevertAid™ reverse transcriptase (Thermo Scientific) and 0.5 µg
20 of oligo-dT in a reaction volume of 40 µl. cDNA synthesis was performed at 37°C for 5 minutes
21 followed by incubation at 42°C for 1 hour and subsequent inactivation at 70°C for 10 minutes.
22 The levels of selected transcripts were determined by RTqPCR in LightCycler 480 (Roche)
23 using LightCycler 480 SYBR Green I Master (Roche) in 10 µl reactions (three technical
24 replicates for each template dilution). Each reaction contained 2 µl of cDNA and 500 nM
25 gene-specific primers (list of used primers is provided in Supplementary Table S1). To avoid
26 possible genomic DNA amplification, we designed primers spanning over exon junctions
27 whenever possible or annealing to distantly positioned exons. We also included reverse
28 transcriptase-free reactions as negative controls. Our data published earlier (Sevcíková *et al.*,
29 2017) showed that transcripts of elongation factor 1α-like as well as polyubiquitin exhibit
30 high stability of expression across organs and conditions in cultivated potato, and thus was
31 proven suitable as reference transcripts for data normalization of qPCR. Based on this we
32 utilized *polyubiquitin (UBI)* mRNA as a reference in this study. The amplification programme
33 consisted of: initial template denaturation, 95 °C 5 min; then 45 cycles (denaturation, 95 °C
34 10 s, primer annealing, 58 °C 15 s, and extension, 72 °C 10 s), followed by melting curve
35 analysis; 97 °C 10 s, 65 °C 1 min followed by slow warming to 97 °C (ramp rate: 0.11 °C/s, 5
36 signal reads per °C). The LightCycler 480 software (version 1.5) was applied to calculate
37 relative copy numbers of the analysed mRNAs in relative quantification mode with standard

1 curves in run. Overview of RT-qPCR assay parameters for WT under both cultivation
2 conditions is summarized in Supplementary Table S2. Additionally, the specificity of
3 amplification with individual primer pairs was analysed by melting curve genotyping and DNA
4 electrophoresis of the respective PCR products.

5 **Phloem exudation**

6 Phloem exudates were collected 21 DAT using *ex vitro* soil cultivated plants (greenhouse) and
7 21, 28 and 41 DAT using tuberization-induced plants in hydroponics under SD. The protocol
8 was based on Tetyuk *et al.* (2013). Whole shoots were cut out by a razor blade near the soil
9 surface and the cut area immersed in MiliQ water. Another transversal section removed air
10 bubbles from transporting tissues. Shoots were then placed in high air humidity conditions
11 and pre-incubated in 20mM K₂EDTA for one hour to prevent plugging of sieve elements. For
12 saccharide determination, phloem exudates were collected in MiliQ water for another one
13 hour. Samples were then dried using a vacuum-evaporator, re-dissolved in 20 µl of MiliQ
14 water and saccharide contents were measured using HPLC as described above. The rate of
15 exudation was expressed as the content of saccharides collected per hour per leaf area unit.
16 For determination of *BEL11* transcript phloem mobility, after K₂EDTA pre-treatment, phloem
17 exudates were collected for one hour in a 1 ml MiliQ water solution containing 80 U.ml⁻¹
18 RNase inhibitor (RiboLock, ThermoFisher), 15% (v/v) protease inhibitor (Complete, Mini,
19 EDTA-free, Roche, 7x stock - 1 tablet dissolved in final volume of 10 ml) and 50 µg.ml⁻¹ linear
20 polyacrylamide (GeneElute, Sigma). To minimize the effect of RNA losses during sample
21 processing, the collected exudates were spiked with a 3µl aliquot of TATAA Universal RNA
22 Spike II spike transcript (TATAA Biocenter AB, Goteborg, Sweden) and then mixed with an
23 equal volume of isopropanol for RNA overnight precipitation at -70°C. Further, samples were
24 centrifuged, the pellet dried and re-dissolved in RNase-free water, RNA was isolated using
25 0.5 ml of TRI reagent and further processed as described above, including cDNA synthesis
26 and RTqPCR. The rate of exudation was expressed as the relative *BEL11* transcript to spike
27 transcript level per plant per hour.

28 **Statistical analysis**

29 Boxplot graphs were generated using JASP software (Version 0.18.3). Error bars in bar charts
30 represent standard deviations. NCSS 9 statistical software (NCSS, LLC. Kaysville, Utah, USA)
31 was employed for data analysis. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used for data meeting the
32 criteria of normal distribution and homogeneity of variance. For data with only biological
33 replicates, One-Way ANOVA was employed. If both, biological and technical replicates were
34 involved, Repeated Measures ANOVA was utilized. In both experimental arrangements, RNAi
35 plants were compared with the control (wild type, WT) using Dunnett's two-sided Test (Versus
36 Control). For data not meeting the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance,

1 or data with low number of replicates, the Kruskal-Wallis Z test (Dunn's test) was used.
2 Statistical significance was determined at $P \leq 0.001$, $P \leq 0.01$, $P \leq 0.05$, and $P \leq 0.1$ levels
3 labelled as ***, **, *, and (*), respectively.

4 Results

5 Selection of BEL11 RNAi transgenic lines

6 Out of ten stably transformed independent BEL11 RNAi lines that were screened for *BEL11*
7 transcript levels (Supplementary Fig. S1A) we selected four lines (lines 1, 10, 12, and 19) with
8 significantly reduced *BEL11* transcript levels (Fig. 1A) and used them for subsequent
9 analyses.

10 Tuberization *in vitro* started earlier in BEL11 RNAi transgenics

11 Tuber induction on node cuttings cultivated *in vitro* under tuber-inducing conditions was
12 monitored weekly (7-35 DAT). Notably, all tested BEL11 RNAi lines (particularly lines 10 and
13 12) exhibited accelerated initiation of tuber formation, though tuberization efficiency at 35
14 DAT did not substantially differ from WT (Fig. 1B). Nevertheless, all four transgenic lines had
15 significantly higher total tuber weights at 35 DAT (Fig. 1C and 1E), particularly due to higher
16 average tuber weight (Supplementary Fig. S1B and S1C). Moreover, all four lines displayed a
17 higher proportion of tuber biomass (51 – 84 %) to the sum of tuber and stolon biomass, in
18 contrast to WT (36 %) (Supplementary Fig. S1D). In accordance with the earlier tuber onset,
19 the transgenic lines (except line 1) showed a higher tendency for sessile (positioned close to
20 the stolon base) tuber formation (particularly in line 10 and 12) (Fig. 1D). Furthermore, all WT
21 stolons exhibited branching, but a portion of transgenic segments (10, 56, 67, and 8% for
22 lines 1, 10, 12 and 19, respectively) produced only non-branched stolons. Overall, these
23 findings indicate a strengthened responsiveness of BEL11 RNAi nodal segments to tuber-
24 inducing conditions *in vitro*, manifested by earlier tuber onset, increased biomass allocation
25 to tubers, and suppressed stolon growth.

26 BEL11 downregulation had an inhibitory effect on tuberization in plants grown under 27 natural-like conditions

28 Motivated by the results showing enhanced tuberization of all BEL11 RNAi lines *in vitro*, we
29 continued with *ex vitro* experiments. In the hydroponic system, first tubers appeared 28 DAT
30 in 67% of WT plants, while in the BEL11 RNAi plants, tuber induction varied from 9 to 50%
31 (Fig. 2A). Moreover, WT showed a trend towards a higher number of swollen stolons - stage 2
32 according to Viola *et al.* (2001) per plant (1.7) compared to the RNAi lines (0.9; 1.2; 0.8 and
33 0.2 for lines 1, 10, 12 and 19, respectively). Even 35 DAT, the average number of tubers in RNAi
34 lines did not exceed that of WT (Supplementary Fig. S2). Total tuber weights per plant 35 DAT

1 were significantly reduced in RNAi lines (Fig. 2B), but the average tuber weights were
2 comparable to that of WT (Fig. 2C). Importantly, the weight of the largest tuber was higher in
3 WT (Fig. 2D). Overall, in the hydroponic system, tuber induction was delayed in the BEL11
4 RNAi lines compared to WT, thus contrasting strongly with the induction under *in vitro*
5 conditions. While both systems enabled simple monitoring of tuber induction, none of them
6 represented natural conditions for potato cultivation. Therefore, we tested also overall
7 tuberization potential of *ex vitro* plants cultivated in soil (both, cultivation chamber and
8 greenhouse) to determine total tuber yield at the end of the vegetative season (130 DAT). For
9 lines 1 and 19, the overall tuber yields, average tuber weights, and the weights of the largest
10 tubers were comparable to those of WT; however, these parameters were significantly lower
11 in lines 10 and 12 (Supplementary Fig. S3 and S4), which in turn exhibited the highest tuber
12 yields *in vitro* (Fig. 1). Although the phenotype of individual transgenic lines was more variable
13 than in previous experiments, greenhouse results matched well with those from the
14 cultivation chamber, confirming stable and reproducible tuberization phenotypes of *ex vitro*
15 soil-grown plants (Supplementary Fig. S3). Strikingly, the above-described phenotype of *ex*
16 *vitro* grown plants was even stronger in tuber-derived plants, with dramatically reduced tuber
17 yields of all RNAi lines to only 15 to 32% of WT (Fig. 3A and 3E). This reduction was linked to
18 a significantly lower number of tubers per plant compared to WT (Fig. 3B). Although we found
19 some aborted tubers (tubers degraded early after initiation of tuber filling) in each genotype,
20 their portion remained consistent across genotypes. Average tuber weights, although highly
21 variable, tended to be lower in transgenics (Fig. 3C) while the weights of the largest tuber
22 significantly decreased in all RNAi lines (Fig. 3D). Altogether, these data further support the
23 observed phenotype of suppressed tuberization in BEL11 RNAi lines *ex vitro*.

24 **BEL11 downregulation led to unexpected changes in the expression pattern of** 25 **tuberization-associated genes**

26 To understand the contrasting behaviour of our mutants under *in vitro* and *ex vitro* conditions,
27 as well as in comparison to previously reported results for ssp. *andigena*, we examined
28 whether it could be linked to different gene expression patterns. Interestingly, leaf *BEL11*
29 transcripts levels were significantly lower in all four RNAi lines under both conditions (Fig. 1A
30 and 4A).

31 Although leaf *BEL11* transcript levels of *ex vitro* plants were reduced in all RNAi lines and this
32 decrease was apparent in phloem sap directed to below-ground organs, particularly in lines
33 with the most suppressed tuberization *ex vitro* (Fig. 4J), *BEL11* transcript levels in stolons
34 exhibited no significant differences (Fig. 4D). However, the levels in roots indicated a
35 decreasing trend, particularly in line 10 (Fig. 4G).

1 Due to reported BEL11's ability to compete with BEL5 and BEL29 for the dimerization partner,
2 POTH1, we further determined their transcripts levels to estimate their potential mutual
3 interrelationships. Unexpectedly, leaf *BEL5* transcript levels significantly decreased in three
4 RNAi lines (line 1, 10, and 12), and line 19 showed a decreasing trend (Fig. 4B). Intriguingly,
5 *BEL11* drop appeared to be stronger, leading to a slight (insignificant) disbalance in the
6 *BEL5/BEL11* transcript ratio in favour of *BEL5* (Supplementary Fig. S5E). In stolons and roots,
7 no significant changes in *BEL5* transcript levels were observed (Fig. 4E and 4H). Similarly,
8 *POTH1* and *BEL29* transcript levels did not differ significantly from WT in any of the tested
9 organs (Supplementary Fig. S5A-D). Furthermore, we evaluated transcript levels of the
10 tuberization inducer *SP6A* and, surprisingly, did not find expected correlation with the
11 phenotype of suppressed tuberization; no significant drop in *SP6A* levels was observed in any
12 organ, rather, a tendency towards increased levels, particularly in lines 10 and 12 (Fig. 4C, F
13 and I).

14 **BEL11 downregulation improved photosynthetic performance and changed biomass** 15 **allocation**

16 As nodal segments cultured in the darkness depend entirely on an external carbohydrate
17 supply from a high-sucrose medium while *ex vitro*/tuber-derived plants rely on their own
18 assimilate production, we further investigated whether the contradictory tuberization results
19 could be ascribed to different way of obtaining and distribution of carbon and energy. In soil
20 cultivated plants, we found substantial differences in several photosynthetic characteristics.
21 Source leaves of all four RNAi lines exhibited significantly higher net photosynthetic rates
22 compared to WT, already under lower irradiance ($300 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and, with
23 increasing irradiance, the differences even deepened (Fig. 5A). Notably, lines 10 and 12 with
24 the strongest tuberization phenotype (weakest tuberization *ex vitro*) displayed the most
25 prominent increases in net photosynthetic rates and exhibited higher contents of
26 photosynthetic pigments (Fig. 5B and Supplementary Fig. S6) with non-impaired maximum
27 quantum yield of chlorophyll a fluorescence (Supplementary Fig. S6).

28 To further understand the reason of non-impaired and even enhanced photosynthetic rate in
29 BEL11 RNAi lines, we determined the carbohydrate contents in tissues and phloem exudates
30 and characterized allocation of carbohydrates to source and sink organs. Surprisingly, in any
31 of the tested organs (leaves, stolons, roots), the carbohydrate content per unit of dry matter
32 did not systematically differ among genotypes, both, in soil and in hydroponics (Fig. 5C-E and
33 Supplementary Fig. S7). Although there was high variability in measured values of
34 carbohydrates in phloem sap that showed a statistical significance only in two lines (Fig. 5F),
35 we repeatedly recorded a clear tendency towards increased levels in all RNAi lines compared
36 to the WT (Supplementary Fig. S8). The carbohydrate composition of the phloem sap,

1 comprising predominantly sucrose, showed no significant differences among genotypes (77-
2 89 %).

3 The higher photosynthetic capacity but unchanged carbohydrate content in tissues, along
4 with a slight increase in carbohydrate contents in phloem exudates in RNAi lines, led us to
5 hypothesize that the difference may lie in biomass allocation. We analyzed non-tuberizing
6 plants (LD, 21 DAT) cultivated *ex vitro* in hydroponics (enabling to harvest the complete root
7 biomass). The total biomass and leaf area of all four RNAi lines were comparable to that of
8 WT (Supplementary Fig. S9), but lines 10 and 12 with the strongest tuberization phenotype
9 showed higher “underground” biomass allocation (“underground” portion of shoot, stolons
10 and roots). This difference resulted from a significantly higher proportion of root biomass in
11 lines 10 and 12, and a trend towards increased root biomass observed in the other two lines
12 (Supplementary Fig. S9). Moreover, significantly enhanced biomass allocation to roots in
13 lines 10 and 12 was observed also in photoautotrophically cultivated *in vitro* plants, reaching
14 26% and 31% of total biomass, respectively, compared to 21% in WT. In contrast to roots, all
15 four transgenic lines showed a significantly decreased allocation to stolons compared to WT
16 (Supplementary Fig. S9). Accordingly, the relative underground biomass allocation to roots
17 over stolons was significantly higher in all RNAi lines (79 to 96 %, compared to 64 % in WT;
18 Supplementary Fig. S9).

19 **BEL11 RNAi lines with the strongest phenotype kept distinct growth dynamics, and** 20 **carbohydrate and transcript patterns even at the stage of tuberization onset**

21 To better understand the BEL11 role in the link of tuberization with metabolic and growth
22 responses, we further followed the course of changes in two developmental stages under
23 tuber-promoting SD: the pre-tuberization stage (28 DAT) and the early tuberization stage (41
24 DAT). Similarly to other *ex vitro* experiments, tuber yields were significantly reduced in mutant
25 lines 10 and 12 and line 19 showed a similar trend (Supplementary Fig. S10). At the pre-
26 tuberization stage, most of the growth response shifts in transgenic lines resembled those
27 observed in non-tuberizing plants under LD (Fig.6, for comparison see Supplementary Fig.
28 S9). At the early tuberization stage, the results were a bit different. All transgenic lines
29 produced more or less similar shoots with comparable number of nodes (Fig. 6B and
30 Supplementary Fig. S11B, similarly to non-tuberizing plants), in lines 10 and 12 accompanied
31 by smaller leaf area (Supplementary Fig. S11A) and reduced total biomass (Fig. 6A).
32 Importantly, lines 10 and 12 persisted the distinct underground phenotype from WT observed
33 in other experiments. In these lines, we again observed a higher proportion of roots (Fig. 6F)
34 and lower stolon biomass proportion (both, decreased number and length) (Fig. 6C, D and
35 F). Accordingly, they also reduced biomass allocation to tubers (Fig. 6F) and exhibited a
36 significant allocation shift favouring roots over stolons and tubers (Fig. 6H).

1 Given the more pronounced phenotype during the transition to tuber onset observed in lines
2 10 and 12, we selected them for other analyses. Notably, we observed significantly lower
3 carbohydrate content per unit of DW in roots at both, pre-tuberization and early tuberization
4 stage, particularly noticeable were lower starch levels in transgenics (Fig. 7B and
5 Supplementary Table S5). This demonstrates a clear enhancement of this trait, compared to
6 non-tuberizing individuals (Fig. 5E). Importantly, assimilate transport towards underground
7 organs does not seem to be compromised at any developmental stage, we even found a trend
8 of elevated carbohydrate levels in the phloem sap (Supplementary Fig. S12). These findings
9 indicate that carbohydrates are utilized for growth instead of being stored in roots, resulting
10 in promoted root growth. In leaves, total carbohydrate levels remained unchanged (Fig. 7A).
11 The total levels in stolons and tubers varied markedly across individual lines being not
12 significantly different among genotypes (Fig. 7C), nevertheless an upward trend in starch
13 level was found in transgenic stolons at the pre-tuberization stage (Supplementary Table S5).
14 Leaf *BEL11* transcript levels predictably decreased in transgenic lines (Supplementary Fig.
15 S13), while, consistently with our previous findings, *SP6A* transcript levels did not correlate
16 with the suppressed tuberization in transgenics; in fact, they exhibited an upward trend in
17 leaves and even a significant increase in young tubers of line10 (Fig. 8).

18 Altogether, biomass allocation in the *BEL11* RNAi lines differed significantly from the WT, with
19 reduced elongation of above-ground stems, suppressed stolon and tuber formation, and
20 enhanced root growth associated with lower carbohydrate content per unit of DW. These
21 alterations became particularly pronounced with the onset of tuberization in lines 10 and 12,
22 which exhibited the most suppressed tuberization, accompanied by an unexpected
23 tendency towards increased *SP6A* transcript levels.

24 Discussion

25 In our study, we analysed the effects of *BEL11* transcription factor downregulation on
26 tuberization in cultivated potato ssp. *tuberosum*. On nodal segments *in vitro*, all tested
27 parameters of tuber induction were promoted in all *BEL11* RNAi lines, thus supporting
28 *BEL11*'s negative regulatory role in tuberization, as reported earlier for ssp. *andigena* (Ghate
29 *et al.*, 2017). However, under *ex vitro* conditions, we revealed a marked contrast as none of
30 the *BEL11* RNAi lines showed enhanced tuberization. In fact, the lines with the strongest *in*
31 *vitro* tuberization (lines 10 and 12) exhibited delayed tuberization and significantly reduced
32 total tuber weights *ex vitro* compared to WT. In tuber-derived plants, the tuberization
33 suppression was even stronger, showing reduced tuber numbers and dramatically lower
34 yields across all RNAi lines. This substantially contradicts the results of Ghate *et al.* (2017),
35 who reported considerably higher tuber yields in *ex vitro* soil-grown *BEL11* RNAi lines of ssp.
36 *andigena*. Surprisingly, until now, only a few studies have compared tuberization phenotypes

1 under *in vitro* and *ex vitro* conditions. For example, Rosin *et al.* (2003) and Kondhare *et al.*
2 (2021) found that ssp. *andigena*, requiring SD conditions for tuberization in soil, was able to
3 tuberize under LD when supplied with sufficient exogenous sucrose *in vitro*. Differences
4 between tuberization under natural and *in vitro* conditions likely reflect distinct source–sink
5 balance under both arrangements. Intact *ex vitro*/tuber-derived plants, which rely on their
6 own assimilate production, exhibit a markedly more complex source–sink interaction. The
7 discrepancy in BEL11's role in the regulation of tuberization between subspecies *andigena*
8 and *tuberosum* can be attributed to their distinct evolutionary histories. Potatoes originated
9 in the Andean region and later expanded globally, requiring adaptations to various day
10 lengths and temperatures (Gutaker *et al.*, 2019; Hardigan *et al.*, 2017). Unlike the strictly SD
11 ssp. *andigena*, modern ssp. *tuberosum* cultivars can tuberize under LD, although
12 tuberization is accelerated under SD. One example of a molecular adaptation of modern
13 cultivars is the presence of truncated *StCDF1* alleles, which have lost day-length dependent
14 regulation (Kloosterman *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, domestication led to substantial changes in
15 the source-sink relationships associated with a dramatic strengthening of the allocation of
16 assimilates to developing tubers and in addition, there are order of magnitude differences in
17 yields between them (e.g. Spooner and Hetterscheid, 2005). Altogether, the data indicate
18 that BEL11's impact on tuberization strongly depends on the particular potato genotype
19 (subspecies) and specific environmental context.

20 To clarify the observed phenomena, we focused on the analysis of expression patterns.
21 *BEL11* transcript levels were significantly reduced in leaves of all RNAi lines regardless of
22 cultivation conditions. Although tendency for lower levels of *BEL11* transcript were also
23 detected in the phloem sap and roots (both particularly prominent in lines with the most
24 distinct tuberization phenotypes), surprisingly, no such reduction was mirrored in stolons
25 and tubers grown *ex vitro*, where *BEL11* levels remained unchanged. The discrepancy
26 between individual organs may be caused by differently efficient *BEL11* silencing, e.g. due to
27 variations in *CaMV* 35S promoter activity driving *BEL11AS* expression (Rahamkulov and
28 Bakhsh, 2020) or decreased *BEL11* transcript accessibility to degradation by the RNA
29 interference machinery, likely resulting from the interaction with RNA-binding proteins (Cho
30 *et al.*, 2015). Since these factors can influence the BEL11 effect in an organ/tissue-specific
31 manner, the interpretation of the observed phenotypes is rather complicated. In this context,
32 it is also necessary to mention that Ghate *et al.* (2017) observed promoted tuberization in all
33 BEL11 RNAi *andigena* lines without a clear correlation with *BEL11* changes in transcript level
34 in stolons or leaves.

35 Another issue that needs to be addressed is the interaction between individual BEL TFs.
36 Importantly, reduced *BEL11* transcript levels in leaves of the RNAi lines were accompanied
37 by down-regulation of *BEL5*, which is considered a positive regulator of tuberization. This

1 *BEL5* drop, which can be connected with the observed phenotype, is undoubtedly not a
2 direct effect of RNA interference. The *BEL11* antisense construct covers a unique 401 bp
3 fragment (of 5' UTR and exon 1) that has practically no sequence similarity detectable by the
4 Basic Local Alignment Search Tool. BEL transcription factors recognise tandem TTGAC
5 motifs in promoter sequences of their target genes and the *BEL5* promoter itself contains
6 these motifs (Chen *et al.*, 2004; Sharma *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, *BEL11* might regulate *BEL5*
7 transcription, although, *BEL11*'s function as a transcription regulator has not been tested yet.
8 Consistently, *BEL11* transcript pattern corresponded to that of *BEL5* in other tested organs
9 (roots and stolons), where both showed no significant changes. Additional support comes
10 from Ghate *et al.* (2017), who described increased stolon *BEL5* transcript levels in transgenic
11 *andigena* with strengthened *BEL11* transport towards stolons. However, understanding the
12 BELs' interactions is further complicated due to a proposed *BEL5* positive regulation of its
13 own transcription in stolons through an autoregulatory loop (Lin *et al.*, 2013). In addition, the
14 transcript levels of both negative tuberization regulators, *BEL11* and *BEL29*, were
15 upregulated in the stolons of *andigena* transgenic lines with induced *BEL5* transcription
16 (Sharma *et al.*, 2016). Altogether, data repeatedly indicate that the expression of various *BELs*
17 may be mutually connected. This could ensure the fine-tuning of target gene transcription in
18 a tissue- and in a developmental stage-specific manner, which is essential for optimal plant
19 performance under various environmental conditions (e.g. Niu and Fu, 2022). Competition
20 for the common BEL interaction partner, *POTH1*, represents another level of hypothetical
21 interactions. Thus, *BEL11* might inhibit tuberization by competing with the positive regulator
22 *BEL5*, as already proposed for *andigena* by Ghate *et al.* (2017). In our mutants, both, *BEL11*
23 and *BEL5* transcript levels decreased in the leaves, while *POTH1* levels remained unchanged.
24 Therefore, we evaluated if changes in expression of these mobile signals could have impact
25 on the expression pattern of the target transcript *SP6A*, coding for key positive regulator of
26 tuberization (Navarro *et al.*, 2011). Interestingly, at stage prior to tuberization, we observed
27 an upward trend in *SP6A* transcript levels in leaves, stolons and roots of the two lines showing
28 the strongest suppression of tuberization. Surprisingly, this pattern became even more
29 pronounced with the onset of tuberization, as in addition to the persistent increasing trend
30 in leaves, a significant sixfold increase of *SP6A* transcript level was detected in transgenic
31 young tubers. These findings, showing that suppressed tuberization in our mutants is not
32 necessarily accompanied by a decrease in *SP6A* levels, suggest a potentially weakened
33 superiority of the *SP6A* signal within the very complex tuberization signalling network in
34 cultivated potato. Interestingly, in another system of spontaneously tuberizing potato line (of
35 cv. Lada), we have previously shown that a multi-fold enhanced *SP6A* transcript level was
36 accompanied by accelerated tuber onset, but reduced overall tuber yield (Fischer *et al.*,
37 2008; Sevcíková *et al.*, 2017). Taken together, our data suggest that the impact of individual
38 tuberization regulators varies in complex regulatory networks of ssp. *tuberosum* and ssp.

1 *andigena*, which precludes simple predictions of the effects of manipulating individual
2 regulatory components as well as an easy interpretation of observed phenotypes.

3 Furthermore, given the wide range of downstream targets of StBEL5, resp. StBEL11, they are
4 likely to influence not only tuberization but also various growth and metabolic processes
5 reflected ultimately in tuber yield. Although, in potato, BEL and FT-like signalizations beyond
6 tuberization have not been extensively studied, in other species, they have been shown to
7 regulate various processes (reviewed by Jin *et al.*, 2021; and Niu and Fu, 2022). For example,
8 in tomato, a close potato relative, the BEL11 and BEL5 homologs (SlBEL11 and SlBEL2) have
9 been shown to act as regulators of photosynthesis by modulating expression of genes
10 involved in chloroplast development (He *et al.*, 2022; Meng *et al.*, 2018; Niu *et al.*, 2022).
11 Photosynthesis impairment would be a possible explanation for the reduced tuber yields
12 observed under natural-like conditions, while tuberization on nodal segments cultivated *in*
13 *vitro* on a high-carbohydrate medium was promoted. Interestingly, we observed no drop in C
14 assimilation efficiency. Instead, photosynthetic rates and pigment levels were higher in
15 BEL11 RNAi mutants, suggesting negative effect of BEL11 (and/or BEL5, which was also
16 down-regulated) on photosynthetic activity, similarly to their tomato homologs. Though
17 increased photosynthesis is often associated with enhanced tuber yields (Ferne *et al.*, 2020;
18 Rosado-Souza *et al.*, 2023), this correlation may not always hold. For instance, potato
19 transgenic lines expressing *Arabidopsis* Hexokinase 1 in guard cells and *SP6A* under a
20 leaf/stem-specific promoter exhibited reduced photosynthetic assimilation, but achieved
21 higher overall tuber yields (Lehretz *et al.*, 2021a).

22 Beyond the capacity for C assimilation itself, downstream processes related to assimilate
23 distribution are equally important, as they ultimately determine biomass allocation to plant
24 organs and therefore affect overall tuber yield (Sonnewald and Ferne, 2018). While at non-
25 tuberizing stage we observed no difference in total biomass, after the onset of tuberization,
26 the two lines with the most pronounced phenotype showed a reduction, accompanied by
27 smaller leaf area. This can influence the overall amount of fixed C, even if the assimilation
28 efficiency per unit of leaf area was increased. Nevertheless, carbohydrate phloem transport
29 to the underground organs did not appear compromised, as indicated by a trend towards
30 increased carbohydrate content in the phloem sap of transgenics at non-tuberizing as well
31 as early tuberization stage resulting in preferential allocation of assimilates to growth of
32 especially underground parts. Typically, in potato, such a pattern of carbon allocation results
33 in simultaneous promotion of root growth and tuberization, e.g. shown in *SP6A* over-
34 expressing lines (Lehretz *et al.*, 2021b), or in plants grown under low nitrate (e.g. Koch *et al.*,
35 2024). The answer to why our BEL11 RNAi plants did not out-perform WT in tuber yield can lie
36 in their altered biomass allocation among the underground organs. In all non-tuberizing RNAi
37 lines, the biomass was preferentially allocated to roots over stolons and similar pattern was

1 preserved till the pre-tuberization stage. At early tuberization, this pattern further persisted
2 in lines with strongly suppressed tuber formation, accompanied by even lower root
3 carbohydrate levels indicating prolonged root growth promotion in these transgenics.

4 Based on the literature data, the cessation of stolon growth occurs concomitantly with the
5 onset of tuberization, but this in itself is not a signal promoting tuber formation (e.g. Struik *et*
6 *al.*, 1988; Xu *et al.*, 1998a; Xu *et al.*, 1998b). One possible cause of limited C allocation to
7 stolons and tubers might be linked with phloem unloading. In roots, saccharides pass
8 through plasmodesmata and symplasmic unloading is directly connected with root growth
9 (e.g. Liu *et al.*, 2024). This would be consistent with our observation of lower root
10 carbohydrate content while biomass accumulation was enhanced, suggesting that
11 utilization for growth may further enhance sink strength. In stolons, unloading is more
12 complicated, starting with the prevailing apoplasmic pathway, where sucrose crosses the
13 membranes by the concerted action of SWEET and SUT transporters, or hexoses (sucrose
14 cleavage products) *via* hexose transporters (reviewed e.g. by Braun, 2022). During the early
15 stages of tuberization, the unloading shifts to symplasmic mode and later returns to a
16 predominant apoplasmic one during subsequent tuber enlargement (Viola *et al.*, 2001).
17 Intervention in *BEL* signalling (modifying transcript levels and mobility together with
18 assimilate flow) can induce changes in gene expression in the underground organs, and
19 consequently alter phloem flow towards roots, underground axillary buds and stolons. The
20 proposed concept of altered carbohydrate flux towards the sink representing a significant
21 component of tuberization regulation network was further supported by experiments in a
22 simplified *in vitro* system, where BEL11 RNAi nodal segments with high carbohydrate supply
23 from medium lacked the competing root sink and exhibited enhanced tuberization. Taken
24 together, the strengthened root growth at the expense of stolons (and subsequently tubers)
25 in BEL11 RNAi lines is likely caused by altered sink strength, possibly connected with phloem
26 unloading efficiencies in root and/or stolon tissues. However, understanding the precise
27 molecular mechanism requires further investigation.

28 If we extend our speculation further and consider an increase in photosynthetic capacity as
29 a primary change stemming from the down-regulation of BEL11, then we can propose the
30 following sequence of events in *ssp. tuberosum* BEL11 RNAi lines. An increase in
31 photosynthetic capacity may generate a signal about C/N imbalance and thus, to strengthen
32 the need for nitrogen uptake, the export of carbohydrates to below-ground is reinforced.
33 Enhanced transport of assimilates downwards usually promotes tuberization. However, due
34 to the above-mentioned different unloading mechanisms in stolons and roots, the signal
35 distribution between them differs correspondingly and, combined with considered stolon-
36 specific changes in *BEL* transcription and activity, causes tuberization restriction.

37

38 **Conclusion**

1 This study clearly demonstrates substantial differences between tuberization regulatory
2 network of the cultivated potato variety (*ssp. tuberosum*) and the experimental potato model
3 of the *andigena* group, emphasizing the impossibility of directly transferring knowledge from
4 one system to another. During the domestication selecting for maximal tuber yields,
5 weakening the strength of certain regulatory factors (such as photoperiod) likely increased
6 the strengths of other signals (generated by metabolic balance and providing indispensable
7 information on plant energetic status) within the complex network governing tuberization.
8 Thus, factors that exhibit a negative function in *ssp. andigena* may have lost this role in the
9 cultivated potato due to the selective pressure. BEL11 could be an example, as it negatively
10 impacts tuber yields in *ssp. andigena*, however, in the cultivated potato, this negative
11 regulatory function appears to be suppressed or even reversed.

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20 **Author Contributions**

21 AZ and PM – designing experiments; AZ, MD and PM – performing experiments; TM –
22 methodology; AZ writing - original and reviewed draft; HL, TM, LF and PM - writing - review &
23 editing.

24 **Conflict of interest**

25 The authors have no conflicts to declare.

26 **Data availability**

27 The raw datasets are freely available in the Zenodo repository
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1 Figure legends

2 **Fig. 1: *BEL11* transcript level and tuberization *in vitro*:** (A) verification of decreased *BEL11*
 3 transcript level in lines 1, 10, 12 and 19; 4-week-old *in vitro* cultivated plants under LD
 4 photoperiod; normalized to the copy number of the reference transcript – polyubiquitin; WT
 5 was set to 1; 3 technical replicates per each cDNA dilution (5x and 50x); (B) timing of tuber
 6 onset; (C) total tuber weight; (D) average distance of tuber to stolon base; (E) appearance of
 7 tuberizing stolons; for (B, C, D and E) node cuttings cultivated *in vitro* on TIM under darkness;
 8 evaluated 7, 14, 21, 28 and 35 DAT (B) and 35 DAT (C,D and E), respectively; WT and four
 9 independent *BEL11* RNAi lines: 1, 10, 12 and 19; for (A) n= 3-11, for (B, C and D) n= 28-30, for
 10 A error bars represent the standard deviations. ANOVA-Repeated Measures Analysis of
 11 Variance (A) or ANOVA-One-Way Analysis of Variance (C and D), Dunnett's Two-Sided
 12 Multiple-Comparison Test With Control was used for statistical evaluation; asterisks indicate
 13 statistically significant differences *** ($\alpha = 0.001$); ** ($\alpha = 0.01$); * ($\alpha = 0.05$); ns (not
 14 significant).

15 **Fig. 2: Tuberization *ex vitro* in hydroponics:** (A) Timing of tuber onset; (B) total tuber weight;
 16 (C) average tuber weight; and (D) average weight of the largest tuber; calculated per plant;
 17 cultivated in hydroponic system under SD photoperiod; evaluated 7, 14, 21, 28 and 35 DAT
 18 (A) and 35 DAT (B,C,D); WT and four independent *BEL11* RNAi lines: 1, 10, 12 and 19; n= 11-
 19 12. ANOVA-One-Way Analysis of Variance, Dunnett's Two-Sided Multiple-Comparison Test
 20 With Control was used for statistical evaluation; asterisks indicate statistically significant
 21 differences *** ($\alpha = 0.001$); ** ($\alpha = 0.01$); * ($\alpha = 0.05$); (*) ($\alpha = 0.1$); ns (not significant).

22 **Fig. 3: Tuberization of tuber-derived plants:** (A) average tuber yield; (B) average number of
 23 tubers; (C) average tuber weight (D) average weight of the largest tuber and (E) and photos of
 24 tubers; (A-D) calculated per plant; (A, C, D and E) involve only vigorous tubers; soil-cultivated
 25 plants under LD photoperiod in the greenhouse, evaluated 130 DAT, WT and four
 26 independent *BEL11* RNAi lines: 1, 10, 12 and 19; n= 9-10. For B error bars represent the
 27 standard deviations; ANOVA-One-Way Analysis of Variance, Dunnett's Two-Sided Multiple-
 28 Comparison Test with Control was used for statistical evaluation; asterisks indicate
 29 statistically significant differences *** ($\alpha = 0.001$); ** ($\alpha = 0.01$); * ($\alpha = 0.05$); ns (not
 30 significant).

31 **Fig. 4: Selected transcripts levels in individual organs and phloem sap:** (A, D, G and J)
 32 *BEL11*, (B, E and H) *BEL5*, (C, F and I) *SP6A*. RNA was isolated from soil *ex vitro* cultivated
 33 plants (cultivation chamber for A-I; greenhouse for J) under LD photoperiod; evaluated 21
 34 DAT, WT and four independent transgenic *BEL11* RNAi lines: 1, 10, 12 and 19; normalized to
 35 (A-I) the copy number of the reference transcript – polyubiquitin, (J) the external spike mRNA;
 36 3 technical replicates per each cDNA dilution (5x and 50x); WT level was set to 1 (mean Δ Ct
 37 values for WT are provided in Supplementary Table S2). n=3-6; error bars represent the
 38 standard deviations. ANOVA-Repeated Measures Analysis of Variance, Dunnett's Two-Sided

1 Multiple-Comparison Test With Control was used for statistical evaluation of data with
 2 normal distribution; Kruskal-Wallis Z test (Dunn's test) was used for data not meeting the
 3 assumptions of normality; asterisks indicate statistically significant differences *** ($\alpha =$
 4 0.001); ** ($\alpha = 0.01$); * ($\alpha = 0.05$); (*) ($\alpha = 0.1$); ns (not significant).

5 **Fig 5: Photosynthetic parameters and carbohydrate contents:** (A) Net photosynthesis rate
 6 under different irradiances, (B) photosynthetic pigment contents (sum of chlorophyll a,
 7 chlorophyll b, and carotenoids). Carbohydrate contents in (C) source leaves, (D) stolons, (E)
 8 roots and (F) phloem sap; *ex vitro* plants cultivated in soil (A-E) in the cultivation chamber, (F)
 9 in the greenhouse; both under LD photoperiod; evaluated 21 DAT, WT and four independent
 10 BEL11 RNAi lines: 1, 10, 12 and 19; n= 3-18, for C-F error bars represent the standard
 11 deviations calculated for total carbohydrate contents. ANOVA-One-Way Analysis of
 12 Variance, Dunnett's Two-Sided Multiple-Comparison Test With Control was used for
 13 statistical evaluation of data with normal distribution; Kruskal-Wallis Z test (Dunn's test) was
 14 used for data not meeting the assumptions of normality; asterisks indicate statistically
 15 significant differences *** ($\alpha = 0.001$); ** ($\alpha = 0.01$); * ($\alpha = 0.05$); (*) ($\alpha = 0.1$); ns (not significant);
 16 in case of A for the last measurement at given irradiance. For statistical analysis of individual
 17 saccharides in the spectra see Supplementary Table S3.

18 **Fig. 6: Growth characteristics at the pre-tuberization and early tuberization stages:** (A)
 19 total DW biomass, (B) average "above ground" shoot length, (C) average number of stolons,
 20 (D) average stolon length, (E and F) pattern of DW biomass allocation in pre- and early
 21 tuberization stage, respectively; (G and H) pattern of dry weight biomass allocation in
 22 "underground" sinks in pre- and early tuberization stage, respectively; plants cultivated in
 23 hydroponic system under SD photoperiod; evaluated at pre-tuberization stage (28 DAT) and
 24 early tuberization stage (41 DAT), WT and four independent BEL11 RNAi lines: 1, 10, 12 and
 25 19; n= 7-11. Error bars represent the standard deviations (A - calculated for total biomass);
 26 ANOVA-One-Way Analysis of Variance, Dunnett's Two-Sided Multiple-Comparison Test With
 27 Control was used for statistical evaluation of data with normal distribution; Kruskal-Wallis Z
 28 test (Dunn's test) was used for data not meeting the assumptions of normality; asterisks
 29 indicate statistically significant differences *** ($\alpha = 0.001$); ** ($\alpha = 0.01$); * ($\alpha = 0.05$); (*) ($\alpha =$
 30 0.1); ns (not significant).

31 **Fig. 7: Carbohydrate contents in individual organs at the pre-tuberization and early**
 32 **tuberization stages:** in hydroponic system under SD photoperiod; pre-tuberization stage (28
 33 DAT) and early tuberization stage (41 DAT), WT and two independent BEL11 RNAi lines: 10
 34 and 12; n= 3-6. Error bars represent the standard deviations calculated for total carbohydrate
 35 contents; ANOVA-One-Way Analysis of Variance, Dunnett's Two-Sided Multiple-Comparison
 36 Test With Control was used for statistical evaluation; asterisks indicate statistically
 37 significant differences *** ($\alpha = 0.001$); * ($\alpha = 0.05$); ns (not significant). For statistical analysis
 38 of individual saccharides in the spectra see Supplementary Table S5.

1 **Fig. 8: SP6A transcript levels at early tuberization stage:** (A) in leaves, (B) in tubers. RNA
 2 was isolated from plants cultivated in hydroponic system under SD photoperiod; evaluated
 3 at early tuberization stage (41 DAT), WT and two independent BEL11 RNAi lines: 10 and 12;
 4 normalized to the copy number of the reference transcript – polyubiquitin, 3 technical
 5 replicates per cDNA dilution (5x); WT level was set to 1 (mean Δ Ct values for WT are provided
 6 in Supplementary Table S2). n= 3-4. Error bars represent the standard deviations; ANOVA-
 7 One-Way Analysis of Variance, Dunnett's Two-Sided Multiple-Comparison Test With Control
 8 was used for statistical evaluation; asterisks indicate statistically significant differences ***
 9 ($\alpha=0.001$); (*) ($\alpha= 0.1$); ns (not significant).

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Figure 1
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Figure 7
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Figure 8
160x47 mm (x DPI)

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